

POTENTIOMETRIC AND VOLUMETRIC ESTIMATION OF PEROXIDES WITH ALKALINE PERMANGANATE

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Peroxide solutions reduce alkaline permanganate in presence of telluric acid to quadrivalent manganese. The method can be used for the potentiometric estimation of peroxides, the errors differing from the acid permanganate method by not more than 0.5%. Another method, which can be applied, consists in mixing the peroxide solution with excess of KMnO_4 , in presence of 0.5 N-NaOH, and 0.2 g. telluric acid, followed by determining the excess oxidant with oxalic acid or ferrous iron.

In the current methods for analysing per-compounds, these are usually converted into hydrogen peroxide through the action of acids whereby the liberated hydrogen peroxide is titrated with a standard permanganate solution. In this investigation it is aimed to determine the peroxide solution by oxidation with alkaline permanganate. Because of the instability of H_2O_2 in alkaline solutions, direct titration of peroxide solution is unsuccessful (Issa and Issa, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, under publication). The procedures followed here consist then in (a) titration of alkaline permanganate solutions with peroxide solutions and (b) mixing the peroxide solution with excess of KMnO_4 , followed by estimating the excess oxidant with a suitable reductant.

EXPERIMENTAL

The peroxide solution (0.1-0.05 N) was prepared by dissolving either barium or sodium peroxide in 0.2-0.4N-HCl. The peroxide content was estimated by titration with permanganate in presence of H_2SO_4 and solid manganous sulphate. 0.1 N- KMnO_4 solution was prepared and standardised by the method of Stamm (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1934, 47, 761).

Procedures

(A). KMnO_4 solution (10-25 c.c.) was mixed with 5 N-NaOH to make the solution 0.5 to 1 N with respect to the alkali hydroxide. Telluric acid (0.2 g.) was then added, the solution well mixed and then titrated with the peroxide solution. The end-point was determined potentiometrically. The apparatus used was similar to that previously described (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 23). The peroxide solution was added dropwise on the permanganate-alkali mixture while continuously stirring the latter. The equilibria were rapidly attained except in the region of the end-point when usually 5-20 minutes were required.

TABLE I

Titration of permanganate in 1 N-NaOH in presence of telluric acid.
 Vol. of $KMnO_4$ soln. taken = 10 c.c.

Titrant.	Conc. of $KMnO_4$.	Max. inflec. per 0.1 c.c. titrant.	End-point		% Error.
			obs.	calc.	
0.0543N- BaO_2 in 0.1N-HCl	0.1099 N	192 mv	12.08	12.11	0.25
0.0271N- BaO_2 in 0.05N-HCl	0.05495	150	12.09	12.14	0.41
0.0945N- Na_2O_2 in 0.2N-HCl	0.1099	222	6.99	6.98	0.15
0.0471N- Na_2O_2 in 0.2N-HCl	0.1099	212	13.98	14.00	0.14
0.09432N- Na_2O_2 in 0.2N- H_2SO_4	0.1099	242	6.97	6.99	0.28

Alkalinity = 1.5N-NaOH.

(B). This procedure involved mixing varying portions of 0.05 N- $KMnO_4$ solution with 0.2 g. of telluric acid ; it was then made 0.5 N with respect to NaOH. This was followed by a known volume of the peroxide solution while continuously shaking the mixture in a 100 c.c. Erlenmeyer flask. The solution was then transferred quantitatively to another 250 c.c. flask containing either a mixture of a known excess of an ice-cold mixture of 0.1108 N oxalic acid or 0.1204 N ferrous iron solution together with 20 c.c. of 4 N- H_2SO_4 . After well mixing, the excess oxalic acid or ferrous iron was titrated with a standard permanganate solution. Table II contains typical data obtained by the above procedure.

TABLE II

$KMnO_4$ = 0.05495 N. Na_2O_2 = 0.0344 N. Oxalic acid = 0.1108 N.
 Ferrous am. sulphate = 0.1204 N.

$KMnO_4$.	Volume of		Potassium permanganate equivalent to				% Error.
	Na_2O_2 .	Oxalic acid	Excess oxalic or ferrous.	Na_2O_2 .	10 c.c. Na_2O_2 . Visual.	New procedure.	
10 c.c.	4 c.c.	10 c.c.	12.68 c.c.	2.51 c.c.	6.26 c.c.	6.28 c.c.	0.32
20	5	10	3.30	3.13	6.26	6.26	0.0
25	10	10	1.43	6.26	6.26	6.26	0.0
10	4	10 ferrous.	11.09	2.52	6.26	6.30	0.64
20	9	10	4.24	5.57	6.26	6.30	0.64

All solutions were made 0.5 N with respect to NaOH after addition of telluric acid.

DISCUSSION

The titration curves of permanganate with the peroxide solutions, as shown in Fig. 1, are characterised by the inflections each. The first inflection is not very

FIG. 1

a—10 c.c.	0.05495 N	× 0.0299 N-Na ₂ O ₂	in 0.05 N-H ₂ SO ₄
b—10	0.04595	× 0.0543	BaO ₂ in 0.1 N-HCl
c—10	0.1099	× 0.0945	Na ₂ O ₂ in 0.2 N-HCl
d—10	0.1099	× 0.0943	Na ₂ O ₂ in 0.2 N-H ₂ SO ₄
e—10	0.1099	× 0.0543	BaO ₂ in 0.1 N-HCl
f—10	0.05495	× 0.0942	Na ₂ O ₂ in 0.2 N-HCl

sharp and corresponds probably to reduction of permanganate to manganate. However, this inflection occurs always later than the theoretical value. The second inflection is quite sharp, amounting in the average to ~200 mv, and corresponds to the reduction of the higher oxidation state of manganese to Mn⁴⁺. It is interesting to remark that the first inflection is sharper in the case of barium peroxide solution than with sodium peroxide, but even then occurs later than that corresponding to theory. This is most probably due to the partial reduction of KMnO₄ to MnO₂. At the second inflection it is found that despite the presence of Ba²⁺ ions, reduction passes completely to MnO₂, indicating that H₂O₂ can reduce the BaMnO₄, originally precipitated. The volume of peroxide consumed till this inflection coincides fairly well with the theoretical values with a maximum error of 0.5% (cf. Table I). The data shown in Table II, which are obtained by procedure (B), are also in good agreement with the acid permanganate method with a maximum error of 0.5%.